

INTELLIGENT BUILDING DESIGN

SHRISHAIL BIRAJDAR¹,

KOMAL PAWAR²,

POOJA MAHINDRAKAR³,

JAYASHRI KALE⁴,

SWAPNALI VHATKAR⁵,

SANDIP RATHOD⁶

¹Asst. Professor, A.G.P.I.T, Solapur.

^{2,3,4,5,6}Civil Engineering Student, A.G.P.I.T, Solapur.

Abstract:

A systems view of building design is a starting point for considering business, space, and building management. An intelligent building helps an organization to fulfill its objectives by facilitating the management of these resources and thereby increasing the effectiveness and efficiency of the organization. At an even more fundamental level intelligent building can copy with social and technological change and also are adaptable to human needs.

Today it has become a household need in the developed world. Intelligent building are designed and managed to meet the challenging environmental, business and human needs. They create environments, which enable their users to achieve their objectives and enhance the potentials of occupants while allowing efficient management of resources with minimum lifetime costs. There has not been sufficient education or enlighten on this style of inter- disciplinary approach to architecture, which could be called a "nouveau-post-modern style".

KEYWORDS: Intelligent building; performance; management; technology; design; human needs; facilities management; systems; automated; building; environment; inter-disciplinary.